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Board Attributes And Its Implications On The Performance Of Deposit Money Banks In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study explored the impact of board characteristics on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria over the period from 2015 to 2024. It focused on assessing how various board attributes, including Board Size (BS), Board Independence (BI), Board Gender Diversity (BGD), and Board Meetings (BM), relate to the financial performance of these banks, specifically using Return on Equity (ROE) as a measure of performance. A sample of 10 banks, selected from the 24 listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group, was used for the analysis. Quantitative research methods were employed, including descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and multiple regression analysis, utilizing the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method. The results indicated that variables such as Board Size, Board Gender Diversity, and Board Meetings had an insignificant impact on ROE. However, Board Independence showed a significant relationship with the banks' financial performance. Based on these findings, the study concludes that there is a significant connection between board characteristics and the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. In particular, it highlights the critical role of Board Independence in influencing corporate outcomes. As a practical recommendation, the study suggests that deposit money banks, particularly in the post-COVID-19 era, should consider reducing their board sizes to around ten members. This approach would not only help minimize the substantial financial costs associated with large boards but also enhance operational efficiency. By adhering to regulatory guidelines while optimizing board structures, banks can potentially improve their overall performance, making them more agile and effective in the evolving economic landscape.

Keywords: Board Size, Board Independence, Board Gender Diversity, Board Meetings and Return on Equity

INTRODUCTION

The financial crisis in Nigeria's banking sector has been attributed to the abuse of corporate governance principles, which has contributed to the failure of numerous banks (Akpokerere&Obonofiemro, 2022). Financial stability and performance are essential for the growth of Nigeria's banking system, as banks play a pivotal role in economic development. They drive growth, provide financing to businesses, and serve as the primary depository for the nation's savings (Ehiedu& Toria, 2022). As the dominant source of debt financing, banks' performance is integral to Nigeria's economic health (Benvolio, 2022). Therefore, improving corporate governance practices, particularly in the banking sector, is critical for fostering economic progress (Faleye et al., 2021).

Corporate governance failures, often linked to ineffective boards, have historically contributed to business instability and corporate collapses in Nigeria (Di-Biase & Onorato, 2021). The board of directors is the highest governing body within an organization, tasked with overseeing company strategy, protecting

shareholder interests, and ensuring long-term profitability. Board composition, including size, independence, and diversity, significantly impacts an organization's performance (Ahmed et al., 2019). The focus on board characteristics, such as independence, has gained increasing attention in corporate governance research, with studies indicating that diverse and well-structured boards enhance corporate performance (Somathiloke, 2018; Rafinda et al., 2018).

In Nigeria, corporate governance reforms have led to changes in board structures, such as the introduction of board diversity and greater emphasis on governance practices (Onuorah & Imene, 2016). However, while the Securities and Exchange Commission has recommended board diversity, no mandatory quotas or guidelines have been established. Given the importance of financial performance in ensuring banks' sustainability, this study aims to explore how board characteristics, specifically size, independence, and diversity, affect the financial performance of Nigerian deposit money banks. The research addresses the gap in literature, as most studies use limited variables to assess board attributes and their impact on financial outcomes, offering mixed results that justify further investigation.

Corporate governance plays a critical role in the banking sector, and its importance has gained global attention due to its impact on improving services and strengthening financial intermediation. Board misconduct, including a lack of proper oversight and self-serving behavior by executive management, has been linked to several bank collapses and the decline in shareholder wealth. In Nigeria, the banking sector experienced significant accounting irregularities in 2009, largely attributed to poor supervisory roles by the board of directors. The boards often delegated control to management, leading to financial distress and routine banking crises (Akpokerere&Obonofiemro, 2022). This highlights the need to examine how board characteristics, such as gender diversity and shareholding, affect the financial performance of listed banks in Nigeria.

The role of the board of directors in establishing the culture, values, and ethics of a company is crucial for aligning the interests of management, shareholders, and other stakeholders to ensure long-term success. While there has been considerable research on corporate governance, studies focusing on board attributes and their effect on performance in Nigeria's banking sector, particularly with respect to board shareholding and gender diversity, are limited. Most research has concentrated on non-financial sectors, with little emphasis on these important monitoring characteristics. This study aims to fill this gap by analyzing the effect of board attributes on the performance of Nigerian deposit money banks over the period 2015-2024, extending the research to include both financial and non-financial firms.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Board Characteristics

A board of directors is a group of individuals elected to represent shareholders, and every public company is legally required to have one. The board is the governing body of a company, responsible not only for its management but also for adopting sound corporate governance practices (Emeka-Nwokeji &Agubata, 2019). Companies with effective boards and competent management that act with integrity are more likely to achieve their business goals and contribute to the economy, as the interests of the board and management are aligned with those of shareholders and other stakeholders (Okolie &Uwejeyan, 2022). For the board to fulfill its duties effectively, it must have a balanced mix of skills and diversity, without compromising on competence, independence, and integrity (Okolie et al., 2022). These factors, referred to as board characteristics, play a key role in research examining the relationship between the board and company performance.

Corporate board characteristics encompass every attribute that enables the board to efficiently pursue and realize the interests of various stakeholders (Pitambar, 2017). The effectiveness of the board can be assessed using both quantitative and qualitative variables. Quantitative variables include board size, independence, shareholdings, meeting frequency, gender diversity, and member competence, while qualitative variables involve factors like decision-making quality and the production of positive outcomes (Kamaludin, Ibrahim & Sundarasan, 2020). A company's board consists of directors appointed by shareholders to oversee the firm's assets and achieve its goals. According to Lin, Luo, and Tang (2015),

this relationship resembles an agency contract, where shareholders, as principals, hire directors to make decisions in their best interests, aiming to maximize profits while ensuring the company's long-term survival.

Financial Performance

Firm performance refers to a company's ability to generate revenue that exceeds its costs in relation to its capital base. A strong and profitable company is better positioned to withstand negative economic shocks and contribute to the stability and growth of the financial system. Ongore and Kusa (2013) defined profitability as the relationship between a company's profits and the investments made to achieve them. They explained that profitability ratios assess how efficiently a company converts its business activities into profits. Profit margins measure the ability to turn revenue into profit, while Return on Assets (ROA) gauges how effectively assets are used to generate net income. Literature also suggests that a lack of confidence in the banking sector's operations negatively impacts performance, typically assessed through metrics like ROA, Return on Equity (ROE), Net Profit Margin (NPM), and Profit After Tax (PAT) (Adigwe, Nwanna & John, 2016; Pitambar, 2017).

Firm performance is an indicator of how effectively an organization utilizes its resources to meet financial objectives (Kang, Ding & Charoenwong, 2021; Yermack, 2021). It reflects the efficiency with which a firm uses its assets to generate profits. There are two key reasons for using firm performance measures: first, profits are closely tied to an organization's long-term financial goals; second, well-chosen performance metrics provide a comprehensive view of the company's overall performance (Thomen & Pedersen, 2000). These outcomes are typically reflected in metrics like Return on Equity (ROE), Return on Assets (ROA), and Earnings Per Share (EPS). In the context of Deposit Money Banks, profitability is commonly assessed using ROA, which measures income generated relative to asset optimization; ROE, which evaluates profit in relation to shareholders' equity; and EPS, which indicates the portion of profit allocated to each share. Among these, ROE is often regarded as the most reliable profitability measure and a key indicator of a company's financial health, as it shows how well management is generating profit from shareholders' equity (Aggei-Mensah, 2018; Nwaiwu & Amah, 2019; Nwaiwu & Joseph, 2020).

Theoretical Review

Agency Theory

Agency theory, introduced by Jensen and Meckling in 1976, centers on the relationship between principals (owners) and agents (managers). It suggests that when a principal hires an agent to perform work, their interests may not align, creating a potential conflict. The principal-agent problem arises from this misalignment, leading to governance issues. The theory emphasizes that business owners need to tie the financial rewards of managers, such as salaries and incentives, to align their interests with those of the shareholders. The difficulty in predicting the behavior of managers, therefore, becomes a key challenge in corporate governance. To address this, the theory advocates for the use of incentive-based compensation, performance monitoring through periodic reports, and adherence to corporate guidelines. While some studies suggest that strong governance can reduce agency costs and improve business performance, others find contradictory results, often due to different methods of measuring governance. This study is grounded in agency theory, highlighting the importance of governance structures in minimizing agency costs and enhancing shareholder value.

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory, proposed by Friedman in 1970, expands on agency theory by recognizing that a business should serve not only shareholders but also other stakeholders, such as employees, customers, and suppliers. Unlike agency theory, which focuses on maximizing shareholder wealth, stakeholder theory argues that a business must balance the interests of all parties involved in its operations. According to this theory, the objective of a firm should be to maximize stakeholder value, considering the social, ethical, and legal contexts within which it operates. Critics of shareholder theory argue that it unfairly prioritizes shareholders over other groups who also contribute to the firm's success, such as employees and suppliers. Stakeholder theory, therefore, emphasizes the importance of satisfying the needs of all

stakeholders, promoting a more inclusive and sustainable approach to corporate governance. It is considered a more comprehensive framework for understanding the role of governance in supporting the long-term success of a company, particularly in relation to its broader societal responsibilities. This study adopts stakeholder theory to connect corporate governance with organizational sustainability.

Empirical Review

Samaila, Latifa, and Onipe (2025) examined the moderating role of ownership concentration on the relationship between board characteristics and the financial value of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study, using data from 9 banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) from 2014-2023, found that board size, independence, and gender significantly impacted financial value, measured by Tobin's Q and Return on Equity. The study recommends limiting board size to a minimum of five members, regulating non-executive directors, and increasing female representation on boards to 30% to improve financial performance.

Okolie and Uwejean (2022) analyzed the impact of board attributes on the financial performance of Nigerian conglomerates from 2011 to 2020. Using panel regression, they found that board size, independence, audit committee size, and shareholdings positively influenced financial performance, while board meetings had no significant impact. The study suggests maintaining a reasonable board size, promoting accountability, and ensuring board independence to enhance financial success. It also recommends limiting board meetings to improve performance.

Benvolio and Ironkwe (2022) explored the effect of board composition on the performance of Nigerian commercial banks from 2011-2021. Their findings revealed that board composition accounted for 85.1% of market value fluctuations. Using various statistical tests, they concluded that board composition significantly impacts firm performance and recommended strengthening corporate governance by ensuring board independence and enhancing the governance structure.

Adegboyegun and Igbekoyi (2022) studied Nigerian manufacturing firms, highlighting the importance of board diversity for financial performance. Using data from 64 firms over 2011-2020, they found that financial expertise diversity improves performance, while other forms of diversity, such as gender or ethnicity, had no significant impact. The study advocates increasing board members with financial expertise to improve long-term company performance.

Eni-Egwu, Madukwe, and Ezeilo (2022) assessed the impact of corporate governance variables on Nigerian listed deposit money banks from 2010 to 2019. They found that board size and audit committee independence significantly influenced financial performance, while gender diversity and board composition had mixed effects. The study recommends reducing board size to 10 members and limiting external board members to improve performance, following regulatory guidelines.

Olaoye and Adeyemi (2021) investigated corporate governance and performance in Nigerian Deposit Money Banks using data from 2008 to 2017. The study found that board size and composition negatively impacted performance, while board audit committees and CEO duality had insignificant effects. Their findings suggest that corporate governance structures significantly influence Nigerian banks' performance, urging better governance practices to improve outcomes.

Hawkar, Akar, Wafa, and Hero (2021) examined the relationship between board qualities and financial performance in Iraq from 2005-2016. Using panel data and multiple regression, the study found that board independence and ownership positively correlated with financial performance, while board meetings negatively affected Return on Assets (ROA). The study recommends keeping more non-executive and independent directors to align shareholder interests and improve performance.

Hafsat and Jibril (2021) evaluated the influence of corporate governance on the financial performance of Nigerian listed deposit money banks from 2011 to 2020. They found that adherence to the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (NCCG) impacted the banks' returns on assets. The study suggests that the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria should develop a more inclusive and flexible corporate governance code to enhance short-term financial performance and long-term economic growth.

Okoye, Olokoyo, Okoh, Ezeji, and Uzohue (2020) studied the impact of governance practices on Nigerian bank profitability, focusing on board size and directors' shareholding. They found that board size,

shareholdings, and company size significantly influenced financial performance. The study recommends optimizing board size to minimize conflicts and suggests that directors maintain substantial ownership positions to support profitable governance practices.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted an Ex-Post Facto research design, which is used when the effect and alleged cause have already occurred, and both conditions are examined retrospectively. This design involves collecting secondary data from the annual reports and accounts of selected banks in the Nigerian banking sector. The study focused on a sample of 10 banks, chosen due to their availability of data and their significance in the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The population initially consisted of all 24 banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as of May 1st, 2024, but due to time constraints and difficulties accessing some banks' annual reports, the study narrowed the sample to 10. These banks (Uba Plc, Zenith Bank Plc, Stanbic IBTC, Access Bank Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, First Bank Plc, Sterling Bank Plc, Eco Bank Plc, Wema Bank Plc, and FCMB Plc) were selected based on their consistent profitability from 2015 to 2024, sound corporate governance practices, and the availability of their annual reports.

Secondary data were collected from the annual reports and accounts of the 10 selected banks for the period 2015-2024. The dependent variable, financial performance, was measured using Return on Assets (ROA), while the independent variables were corporate governance factors, including Board Size (BS), Board Independence (BI), Board Gender Diversity (BGD), and Board Meetings (BM). The study utilized descriptive statistics and correlation analysis to determine the relationships between the independent and dependent variables. For hypothesis testing, the study employed multiple regression analysis using the OLS method, with the pooled, random, and fixed-effect models applied through E-VIEW 9.0 software. This approach was used to explain how variations in the independent variables (corporate governance factors) influenced changes in the dependent variable (ROA) over time.

The model specification was adapted from the work of Eni-Egwu, Madukwe, and Ezeilo (2022), and was expressed as:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS + \beta_2 BI + \beta_3 BGD + \beta_4 BM + e$$

Where ROA represents Return on Assets, BS stands for Board Size, BI denotes Board Independence, BGD is Board Gender Diversity, BM refers to Board Meetings, and e is the error term. The coefficients β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , and β_4 are expected to be either greater than or less than zero, indicating the direction and magnitude of the relationships between the corporate governance variables and financial performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the empirical findings based on the panel data from ten (10) Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, covering the period from 2015 to 2024. Secondary data was obtained from the audited annual financial reports of the selected banks, structured into a panel format to capture both cross-sectional and time-series variations. This approach allowed for a detailed analysis of the relationship between key corporate governance factors such as Board Size (BS), Board Independence (BI), Board Gender Diversity (BGD), Board Meetings (BM), and financial performance, measured by Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE).

Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics of the study comprises of the minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation of the coefficients were described. The summary of the descriptive statistics are shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Descriptive statistics output of the Independent and Dependent Variables

	ROE	BS	BI	BGD	BM
Mean	5.670398	13.64000	0.516605	0.198180	3.040000
Median	0.119076	14.00000	0.500000	0.200000	3.000000
Maximum	149.0832	20.00000	0.857143	0.416667	5.000000
Minimum	-3.943182	8.000000	0.166667	0.055556	2.000000
Std. Dev.	25.27803	2.721111	0.179075	0.066926	0.345826
Skewness	4.520321	0.337761	0.481335	0.207718	2.104239
Kurtosis	22.34558	2.635093	2.469479	3.294921	16.06045
Jarque-Bera	1880.937	2.456194	5.034105	1.081526	784.5272
Probability	0.000000	0.292849	0.080697	0.582304	0.000000
Sum	561.3694	1364.000	51.66051	19.81803	304.0000
Sum Sq. Dev.	62619.94	733.0400	3.174729	0.443426	11.84000
Observations	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Researcher Computation using E-VIEW 9.0, 2025.

The data set consists of 100 observations from ten listed deposit money banks on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, covering the period from 2015 to 2024. Descriptive statistics for the independent variables—Board Size (BS), Board Independence (BI), Board Gender Diversity (BGD), and Board Meetings (BM)—and the dependent variable, Return on Equity (ROE), show various trends. BS ranges from 8 to 20, with a mean of 13.64 and a standard deviation of 2.72, indicating significant variation. BI ranges from 0.1667 to 0.8571, with a mean of 0.5166 and a standard deviation of 0.1791, suggesting moderate volatility. BGD shows values between 0.0556 and 0.4167, with a mean of 0.1982 and a standard deviation of 0.0669, reflecting a slight increase over time. BM range from 2 to 5, with a mean of 3.04 and a standard deviation of 0.3458, showing relatively low volatility. ROE varies widely from -3.9432 to 149.0832, with a mean of 5.6152 and a standard deviation of 25.1561, indicating high volatility. Kurtosis analysis shows that BS, BI, and BGD have peaked distributions, while ROE and BM exhibit flatter distributions.

Correlation Results

The section presents the correlation result of the explanatory variables with elaborate explanations. The correlation matrix is used to examine the linear relationship between the independent and dependent variables and also between the independent variables. The study therefore adopted person correlation coefficient to assess the level of association between the variables concerned. The table 2 shows the correlation between the dependent variable; financial performance [proxied with ROE] and independent variables; board characteristics [BS, BI, BGD and BM].

Table 2: The Correlation Matrix for the Variables under Study

	ROE	BS	BI	BGD	BM
ROE	1.000000				
BS	0.090187	1.000000			
BI	0.176590	0.333091	1.000000		
BGD	0.006420	-0.458855	0.307080	1.000000	
BM	-0.025909	-0.264847	-0.074726	-0.029419	1.000000

Source: E-VIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

The correlation analysis reveals a strong positive relationship between BS and ROE, with a coefficient of 0.0902, indicating that a larger board size helps determine a bank's ROE capacity. BI also shows a positive correlation with ROE, with a coefficient of 0.1766, suggesting that greater board independence leads to higher ROE. BGD has a strong positive correlation with ROE, with a coefficient of 0.0064, implying that an increase in female representation on boards enhances ROE. Conversely, BM shows a weak negative correlation with ROE, with a coefficient of 0.0259, indicating that excessive meetings do not necessarily improve a bank's ability to generate higher ROE. The correlation matrix confirms the

absence of multicollinearity among the variables, with no correlation exceeding 0.7. Thus, BS, BI, and BGD positively affect ROE in Nigerian DMBs.

Fixed Effect Regression

Fixed Effect Regression is a statistical technique used in panel data analysis to estimate the relationship between variables while controlling for unobserved, time-invariant characteristics specific to each entity. This method focuses on the variation within each entity over time, eliminating bias from variables that do not change over time. It is particularly useful when analyzing data with multiple entities and time periods, such as firms over several years, ensuring that the estimated effects are not influenced by unobserved heterogeneity across entities.

Table 3: Regression Results of the Independent and Dependent Variables

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests

Equation: Untitled

Test cross-section fixed effects

B

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	7.079499	(9,85)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	55.378990	9	0.0000

Cross-section fixed effects test equation:

Dependent Variable: ROE

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 05/17/22 Time: 20:57

Sample: 2015 2024

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 10

Total panel (unbalanced) observations: 99

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	8.182685	38.65846	0.211666	0.8328
BS	0.613008	1.149666	0.533205	0.5952
BI	26.05345	12.57997	2.071026	0.0478
BGD	35.01278	44.11306	0.793705	0.4294
BM	-1.413235	7.835283	-0.180368	0.8573

R-squared	0.339654	Mean dependent var	5.670398
Adjusted R-squared	0.115365	S.D. dependent var	25.27803
S.E. of regression	25.29335	Akaike info criterion	9.348145
Sum squared resid	60136.84	Schwarz criterion	9.479212
Log likelihood	-457.7332	Hannan-Quinn criter.	9.401175
F-statistic	0.970335	Durbin-Watson stat	1.945530
Prob(F-statistic)	0.427606		

Source: E-VIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

The regression results show a positive relationship between BS and ROE, with a coefficient of 0.6130. However, the p-value of 0.5952 exceeds the 0.05 significance level, indicating no statistically significant relationship between the two variables. This finding suggests that, despite a larger board size being positively correlated with higher ROE, the relationship is not strong enough to be considered significant.

This result aligns with Agency Theory, which emphasizes the importance of aligning managerial interests with those of shareholders. Larger boards may offer a variety of perspectives and oversight, but the lack of statistical significance indicates that the optimal board size may vary, as noted in the empirical review by Samaila, Latifa, and Onipe (2025), who recommend a minimal board size to improve governance and performance. Their findings emphasize the importance of board independence and size in determining firm value, suggesting that while board size may impact financial performance, other factors like independence and gender diversity might be more influential.

BI shows a strong positive relationship with ROE, with a coefficient of 26.0534 and a p-value of 0.0478, which is less than the 0.05 significance level, indicating a statistically significant relationship. This result suggests that higher board independence positively influences ROE, as non-executive directors provide unbiased oversight, helping to improve the bank's financial performance. This finding is consistent with Agency Theory, which posits that independent boards reduce agency costs by ensuring that managerial actions are aligned with shareholder interests. Benvolio and Ironkwe (2022) found that board independence significantly impacts firm performance in Nigerian commercial banks, echoing this study's results. The positive impact of board independence on ROE reinforces the idea that independent oversight is crucial for achieving better financial outcomes, as recommended by Olaoye and Adeyemi (2021), who suggest that a more independent board structure enhances corporate governance and bank profitability.

The relationship between BGD and ROE shows a positive correlation, with a coefficient of 35.0128, but the p-value of 0.4294 exceeds the 0.05 significance level, indicating that the relationship is not statistically significant. This implies that increasing the proportion of women on the board may not necessarily lead to a significant change in ROE, although it is generally associated with improved governance. Stakeholder Theory helps explain this finding, suggesting that businesses should prioritize the interests of all stakeholders, including shareholders, but gender diversity may not be a primary driver of financial performance. The results align with Adegboyegun and Igbekoyi (2022), who found that while financial expertise diversity positively influences performance, gender diversity did not have a significant impact. However, promoting gender diversity remains crucial for improving governance, as suggested by Samaila, Latifa, and Onipe (2025), who recommend increasing female board representation to 30% to enhance governance and financial performance.

BM exhibit a negative relationship with ROE, with a coefficient of -1.4132 and a p-value of 0.8573, indicating no statistically significant effect. This suggests that increasing the frequency of board meetings does not necessarily correlate with better financial performance. According to Agency Theory, while frequent meetings may be expected to enhance oversight, excessive meetings could be inefficient and may indicate poor management or decision-making processes. This finding is consistent with Okolie and Uwejeyan (2022), who observed that board meetings had no significant impact on the financial performance of Nigerian conglomerates. The lack of significant correlation suggests that focusing on the quality of board decisions, rather than meeting frequency, is more important for improving ROE. This aligns with the recommendations of Benvolio and Ironkwe (2022), who suggest that enhancing the overall governance structure, rather than increasing meetings, is key to boosting performance.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the impact of board attributes on the financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria, focusing on BS, BI, BGD, and BM. The findings reveal that while Board Size and Board Gender Diversity show positive correlations with ROE, they do not have a statistically significant impact on performance. Board Independence, however, demonstrates a significant positive relationship with ROE, underscoring the importance of independent oversight in enhancing financial outcomes. Conversely, Board Meetings exhibit a negative relationship with ROE, suggesting that more frequent meetings do not necessarily lead to better financial performance. These findings highlight the need for Nigerian banks to optimize board size, ensure greater independence, and focus on the quality of board decisions rather than meeting frequency. The study reinforces the relevance of Agency Theory, which stresses the alignment of managerial and shareholder interests, and Stakeholder Theory, which advocates for inclusive governance

practices. Overall, the research contributes valuable insights for improving corporate governance structures in the Nigerian banking sector to enhance financial performance and align with best practices.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. **Board Size:** The study suggests optimizing board size, as larger boards may offer diverse perspectives but may not guarantee better performance. The recommendation is to adopt a minimal board size in line with regulatory guidelines for improved efficiency and governance.
- ii. **Board Independence:** The study highlights the importance of enhancing board independence to improve performance. Banks should prioritize recruiting more independent directors to foster unbiased oversight, which would likely align managerial actions with shareholder interests.
- iii. **Board Gender Diversity:** While gender diversity has not shown a significant effect on ROE in this study, it remains essential for improving governance. Banks are encouraged to increase female representation on boards to foster diverse perspectives and inclusive decision-making, which can enhance long-term governance and stakeholder satisfaction.
- iv. **Board Meetings:** The study indicates that frequent board meetings do not necessarily enhance performance. Banks should focus on improving the quality of board discussions and decisions rather than increasing the frequency of meetings, ensuring that boards are more strategic and less procedural in their operations.

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